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Experiences from a multidisciplinary student project with simulated robots and digital project work

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ABSTRACT

The challenges of software engineering for cyber-physical systems (CPS) are hard to teach in normal lectures. To understand, students have to experience these challenges by themselves. Thus, we offer a project where students have to develop a multi-robot system in a small team. Besides the challenging task, the students also have to face the challenges of multidisciplinary project work and have to give convincing presentations of their progress. Due to Covid-19, we have converted our project into an online project with simulated robots instead of real hardware. Students have to record their milestone presentations and upload them to the learning platform Moodle. Other students can ask questions about the presentations and have to review assigned presentations. During the project work, we support the students with supervised online meetings and modern tools for software engineering. As an introduction into project management, we provide an interactive lesson on Moodle. Our experiences have shown that the usage of simulated robots increases the creativity and the spectrum of topics, e.g. industry 4.0 or autonomous driving, as no hardware has to be purchased and ideas can be tested quickly in the simulator. The online meetings provide a spatial and temporal flexibility that enables students with Family commitments to participate. The asynchronous format of the milestone presentations also increases the flexibility and lowers the inhibition threshold for the communication between students. We have also witnessed an increase in the quality of student talks that was caused by the possibility to record the talks several times.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Many things in our daily life, like household appliances, cars or multimedia devices, and in the industry, e.g. automated production, are controlled by cyber-physical systems. Nonfunctional requirements like concurrency, real-time behavior or heterogeneity, as well as the complexity of the physical processes that need to be controlled, make software engineering for embedded systems a challenging task. With the increasing connectivity and automation of these systems, even more engineering challenges arise. Moreover, the ability to work in multidisciplinary teams [1] and remote collaboration become increasingly important. These challenges and the required abilities to meet them are hard to teach in traditional lectures. Instead, they require new formats. To meet these challenges, we usually offer a project where students have to develop a multi-robot system in a small multidisciplinary team (see [2]). Besides completing a challenging task, the students also have to organize project work and give convincing presentations of their progress. Our target group are students of Computer Science, Computer Engineering, and other related degree programs (e.g. Automotive Systems) at the end of their bachelor studies or in their master studies. Bachelor students focus on embedded software engineering and master students focus on quality assurance for safety-critical applications and on optimization for real-time and restricted resources, like memory or energy. We make sure that the groups include students with different degrees and majors, to enable transfer learning and let students practice work in diverse teams. To us, this is among the essential experiences of our project and highly valuable to a future career in the industry, as also highlighted in [1].

Due to Covid-19, we were forced to develop a concept for teaching the same skills in an online environment with simulated robots instead of real hardware. In this paper, we present our concept and first experiences with seven project groups in summer 2020 at TU Berlin. Our experiences show that using simulated robots increases the creativity and the spectrum of topics, e.g. industry 4.0 or autonomous driving, as no hardware has to be purchased and ideas can be tested quickly in the simulator. In the previous format four groups had to share five LEGO Mindstorms robots and one project room. To solve multi-robot tasks they had to agree on 1-2 robot designs and assemble them themselves, thus limiting both the range of available topics and the motivation to test different designs. Moreover, the online project meetings provide a spatial and temporal flexibility that enables students with family commitments to participate. We have also witnessed an increase in the quality of many student talks that was caused by the possibility to record the talks several times.

We first present our course concept in Section 2 and then summarize our experiences and results of our course evaluation in Section 3. We end with a conclusion in Section 4.

2 ONLINE COURSE CONCEPT

The aim of our project is to teach the students to work together in a team of 5-8 students on a complex embedded software design task. Besides the challenging embedded software design task itself, we want the students to gain experience in project management and organization. They should learn how to plan work packages and interfaces so that multiple teams can work on subsystems, which are later integrated into one system. Furthermore, they gain experience in milestone presentations and learn how to give constructive feedback on the presentations of the other project groups. We offer different project tasks that are related to current research topics in embedded system design, such as autonomous systems and AI, or quality assurance and programming of safety-critical control tasks. The application areas range from autonomous exploration and rescue robots over autonomous cars to industry 4.0. With this, we can integrate recent research results in teaching and inspire students for research.

In the following subsections, we first introduce our course structure and then go into details

on how we organized online teaching and online project work. Afterwards, we describe our asynchronous presentation mode and how we kept students involved in the course organization with continuous feedback.

2.1 Course Structure

Figure 1: Course Structure and Online Realization

Figure 2: Virtual robot design of a student group

Our project is worth 9 credit points (ECTS) and consists of two parts: a project with 6 ECTS and a seminar with 3 ECTS (Figure 1). In the project part, the students work on their project task with a focus on embedded software design and quality assurance. To increase the team effectiveness, we have included some recommendations from team effectiveness research [3] on grading and project management. The grades reflect individual effort (avoids social loafing), participation in management tasks, and the ability to explain all aspects of the project in an oral exam (promotes collaboration and communication). Students have to manage their project as a team. They have to divide the challenging task into sub-tasks and agree on a project plan. They have to define responsibilities for time, resource and technical project management and agree on strategies for integration and quality assurance. To support them, we have weekly supervised project meetings, where we observe the current state and give hints to solve problems before they become critical. In the seminar part, the students read and discuss recent research articles on the project task, present their project progress in milestone presentations and review presentations of their fellow students.

For our online course, we have carefully transferred all course elements into online activities. As the general restrictions due to Covid-19 already challenge all participants, we put a special focus on offering great flexibility while maintaining a realistic project setting and offering important experiences. In the following, we go into details on our online activities.

2.2 Online Teaching

Traditionally, we began our project with introductory lectures on project management fundamentals and the Lego Mindstorms environment. For the updated project, we provide material on the learning platform Moodle instead. We created a mandatory interactive training lesson on project management with the same content as our lecture but with the material split into small sections that students can take repeatedly and at their own time. After each section, we provide study questions for self evaluation. For Webots, we exploit the extensive material already available online and select and link suitable tutorials and documentation. Moreover, we provide additional learning material and research papers related to the project topics.

2.3 Online Project Work

In our original project, teams met regularly to work on LEGO *Mindstorms* robots [2]. To enable collaboration in our online project, we replace all physical hardware with the open-source robot

simulator *Webots*¹[4]. Figure 2 shows the *Webots* GUI with a robot design from our summer 2020 project. Robot simulators like *Webots* or *Gazebo*² have proven effective in educational projects [5, 6]. They provide many advantages over actual hardware, like faster prototyping, integration with automated tests, and no physical or monetary limitations on the robot and environment design. Hence, compared to previous topics like maze exploration or autonomous driving on a track, they also allow us to provide more diverse tasks, including areas of current research, like *Reinforcement Learning* [7].

In addition to *Webots*, we offer students a suite of modern software engineering tools. We choose tools that ensure privacy of student data and communication, and that are commonly used in the industry. For communication within groups and with us, we provide messaging with group forums on Moodle and the tool *Slack*³, and the video conferencing solutions *Zoom*⁴ and *Jitsi*⁵. Moodle group forums and Slack enable students to communicate asynchronously, so that they do not need to respond immediately. For project resource and time management, we offer access to the development platform *Gitlab*⁶. Gitlab integrates version control, issue tracking, and continuous integration. Jitsi and Gitlab instances are hosted by TU Berlin, and Slack communication and Zoom conferences are encrypted, guaranteeing privacy.

Putting remote collaboration at the center greatly increases flexibility. Previously, students had to compete for a limited number of project rooms in order to meet. If a room was booked by another group, they had to reschedule. Also, many students lived in different areas and had to take a long journey across the city if they wanted to meet, requiring careful planning in advance. In our project, students can communicate more frequently and spontaneously, because all communication is online and does not always require a direct response. With this new flexibility in time and place, we also allow more groups of students to participate. This includes students that are abroad or have restricted schedules, e.g., due to childcare. Finally, experiencing remote collaboration with state-of-the-art tools and methods gives our student a great advantage for later work in the industry, where distributed software development has been common practice for many years.

Remote collaboration also allows us to get an overview of a current project status and student contributions more easily, because Gitlab tracks all changes to code and documentation. Thus, by analyzing this data, we can estimate the current and overall workload per team member, to give fair grades. Moreover, we can identify problems with time management and raise attention to these early during the semester, so that the group can work on these and still deliver a successful product. We can also analyze most group communication because Slack and Moodle record all discussions. Based on this data, we can identify students that participate frequently or rarely, as well as potential conflicts.

2.4 Milestone Presentations

We complement online project work with three milestone presentations during the semester, where students should exchange ideas and improve their presentation skills. In the previous format, the groups presented their work in succession on fixed milestone days, with a short discussion after each presentation. Now, we updated this process to an asynchronous format. Instead of presenting in person, groups record their presentations as video. Each video should feature 2-3 speakers, with a length of about 25 minutes. We publish all videos on our course page on Moodle and provide three channels for discussion and feedback. For content related questions, students can comment publicly on presentation videos. Each student must ask at least one question per milestone, to initiate discussion. In turn, each group must answer all questions related to their videos. For feedback on the presentation, we provide anonymous

¹ <http://www.cyberbotics.com>

² <http://gazebo.org/>

³ <https://slack.com>

⁴ <https://zoom.us>

⁵ <https://jitsi.org>

⁶ <https://about.gitlab.com>

review forms about the form of the presentation and performance of the speakers on Moodle. Each student must review presentations of two other groups per milestone. We assign these groups randomly and uniformly, so that all groups receive the same amount of feedback. We collect all reviews and send them to the corresponding groups. Finally, all supervisors give feedback to each speaker.

Our asynchronous milestone process has many benefits. Recording presentations in advance gives students the chance to improve their presentation skills more easily. They can watch their recording and retake problematic sections. Also, other students and supervisors can pause between presentations and watch videos repeatedly, allowing them to focus on different aspects, and thereby, asking more detailed questions and writing more helpful feedback. This feedback can also be more critical. As reviews are anonymous, students must not fear spirited reactions from other students. At the same time, we ensure that reviews are objective and do not contain insults before sending them to the reviewed groups. Moreover, our text based feedback process enables students that are not fluent in English to participate easily.

2.5 Final Presentation

At the final presentation at the end of the semester, students should learn how to present their finished product convincingly and creatively to outsiders and potential customers. We split this presentation in two common formats, a video and a website. The video should be 15 minutes long and show all product features in action. The website should give an overview of project goals, major design decisions, and results. We evaluate the submissions by content, creativity, and appeal. As incentive, we publish all websites on our research group site. Moreover, we hold a contest, where students and supervisors elect the best website and video anonymously (students cannot vote for their own group). We show the winning video on our research group site and highlight the winning website with a prominent banner.

2.6 Continuous Feedback

Our primary objective is to deliver a project that is effective in teaching and enjoyed by our students. However, we do not yet know if our new teaching methods work as intended. Therefore, we collect and evaluate student feedback continuously throughout the course and adapt our approach where necessary. We collect feedback from three sources. First, we use the feedback activity type built into Moodle to collect data through anonymous surveys. Second, we discuss our methods with students in our weekly group meetings. Third, we use data collected by Moodle, like the view counts from milestone presentation videos. These allow us to identify formats that work well, or ones that need improvement, e.g., as indicated by low engagement. After collecting the feedback, we respond to it, for instance, by discussing it, or adjusting our methods. Thereby, we increase the quality of our teaching continuously. Also, we show that we value the needs and opinions of our students, resulting in more feedback and a friendly and productive atmosphere.

3 EVALUATION

Figure 3: Participants of the project in 2020 by major

We implemented our project at TU Berlin in summer 2020 with 19 bachelor and 23 master students. Figure 3 shows the distribution of their majors. As it can be seen, most of our 42 participants were enrolled in *Automotive Systems* (16), *Computer Engineering* (12), and

Computer Science (9). The remaining participants majored in *Mechanical Engineering* (1), *Economical Engineering* (1), *Mathematics* (1), *Information Systems Management* (1), and *Innovation in Information and Communication Technology* (1). After an initial vote for a project topic, we assigned the students to 7 teams with 5-7 members each.

Overall, our project was received very well. At the end of the project, we asked all students to give us feedback in an anonymous survey on Moodle. Almost all of the 17 respondents were very satisfied with the project in general and our supervision. 14 rated the project *good/very good*, only three students thought the project was just *satisfactory*. No student chose *sufficient* or *weak*. Most students were also satisfied with our supervision. 13 students thought it was *good/very good*, three rated it *satisfactory*, and only one student thought it only was *sufficient*. No participant thought it was *weak*. We also asked students how much they learned about project management and teamwork. They could respond *very much*, *much*, *some*, *not much* or *little*. The results indicate that our use of large, diverse teams is effective. 14 of 17 participants said they learned *much/very much* about project management. Only three said that they learned *some*. Similarly, almost all participants appear to have improved their teamworking skills. Four respondents said that they learned much and nine even learned very much. Only four students responded with *some*, but no one chose *not much* or *little*. Also, 11 students answered that they have learned much/very much about interdisciplinary teamwork. Four students learned some, while two students said they did not learn much about it.

We evaluate our teaching methods in more detail in the following, using data from our continuous feedback process. We use two anonymous surveys with 24 and 35 participants, respectively, that we published after the first and second milestone, and our final survey, with 17 participants. In addition, we use oral feedback from our weekly and final group meetings, and internal statistic from our course page on Moodle.

3.1 Online Teaching

Our introductory lesson on project management was very well received. After completing the lesson, 98% of our participants expected it to be helpful during the project. We did not ask about the lesson in the final feedback again, but several students reported that it had helped them. Our additional learning material was also welcomed.

3.2 Online Project Work

The online project work mostly met our expectations. All teams were creative and explored different robot and environment designs in Webots. Still, many groups would have preferred to have both a simulation and physical hardware. No physical hardware also meant that students could not gain experience in low-level embedded programming with resource constraints, a key component of this project previously. However, it gave them more time for other equally important aspects, including algorithm design and quality assurance. Still, this additional time was limited, due to new tasks like environment design or continuous integration.

As expected, remote collaboration requires more coordination and discipline within the teams. As in a normal project, team members in an online environment must be able to work on features in parallel, and integrate these features later easily. This requires components with well defined interfaces, and regularly testing, to ensure that components satisfy their specification. Otherwise, the team cannot share the workload effectively and likely fails to complete the project in time. In an online environment, specification and testing are even more important, because group members cannot meet in person and regularly test the integrated product when collaborating virtually. This was a challenge to some groups. One group in particular defined interfaces very late. Consequently, they could not distribute work effectively, because some students waited for components from other students, that these were still working on. They

also failed to integrate their components later, due to incomplete testing. Ultimately, they met in person and integrated most features manually. Most teams that defined interfaces and set up continuous integration with unit tests early, in contrast, could distribute work effectively and meet their project plan.

All groups also exploited the flexibility of online communication. All groups communicated on Slack. Often, groups split into smaller teams, and met in these subgroups. From the communication on Slack, we know that there were several spontaneous meetings, often at least once per week. Moreover, we had several students from China that could not leave their country due to Covid regulations but were still able to participate in the project. Despite this flexibility, most students would still prefer to meet their team members in person. In our final survey, only seven of 17 students said they would continue to meet online. The student feedback from our final group meetings also supports this.

Finally, remote collaboration simplified supervision, as we hoped. Often, we could get an accurate overview of the current project status by looking at open issues and the continuous integration pipeline on Gitlab, and discussions on Slack. Moreover, using the tool *Gitinspector*⁷, we could often identify individual project contributions, allowing us to ask more directed questions during the oral consultation at the end of the project. However, we observed that the commits to the repository did not always provide us an accurate view. Some students were using the same Gitlab account, because they met in person and worked on the same computer, or could not access the repository themselves, due to regulations. Hence, their contributions were associated to another person. Therefore, although intended, we could not use the Gitlab statistics as direct input for the final grade.

3.3 Milestone Presentations

Our updated milestone presentation format increased the general quality of most student talks and feedback, and lead to more engagement. A direct comparison of grades with previous years is not possible, as we have modified our evaluation criteria.

(a) Unique video views (dashed line = mean)

(b) Total video views and comments

(c) Video comments (dashed line = mean)

Figure 4: Student engagement with group presentations across milestones

As intended, many groups took advantage of the asynchronous format and submitted appealing and skilled presentations. As shown in Figure 4a, these presentations attracted much interest. At the first milestone, most of our 42 course participants watched all videos, although not required. The view counts declined at the second and third milestones, but all but one video were still seen by at least 42% of all participants. Hence, giving all groups large audiences. Likely, most students wanted to get a general overview of all groups at the first milestone and

⁷ <https://github.com/ejwa/gitinspector>

then focused on the teams they were interested in. The aggregated views per milestone (figure 4b) show that students watched videos repeatedly, as we intended. We also exploited this feature and found that pausing and rewinding allowed us to give more precise feedback.

Our review process led to high engagement as well, likely due to our incentives and lower language barriers. Similar to a real discussion, not all viewers commented on all videos and not all videos received an equal number of comments (see figure 4c). However, all groups received at least a few questions. Students commented most at the first milestone (see figure 4b). There, they asked significantly more questions than we required. This correlates with the view counts and our experience. At the first milestone, students are still in the concept phase of the project and open to input from others. Despite that, 12 of 24 respondents of our first survey thought that the comments were not an adequate replacement for live discussions. During the semester, most students also valued the reviews. In our first survey, most students agreed that writing (67%) and receiving (96%) reviews helps them to improve their own presentation skills. However, we found that some reviews were very unspecific, and many students complained about an overwhelming workload. In response, we updated the review form and reduced the required reviews from three to two. In subsequent feedback, 91% of 35 respondents confirmed that the workload was now manageable. Also, 77% said that our updated form helps them to formulate their feedback more precisely. Likewise, we observed an increase in feedback quality. Still, at the end of the semester, several students criticized that they received imprecise and duplicate feedback, but according to one student, the large quantity of reviews meant that there were always at least a few helpful among them.

Despite this engagement, most participants of our final survey would not continue with the current asynchronous milestone format. Only seven of 17 respondents would keep video presentations and only five would have anonymous student reviews. Based on oral feedback, we assume that the effort required for recording and cutting the videos, and writing reviews are the primary reasons for this. Still, 11 respondents would keep video comments.

3.4 Final Presentation

For the final presentation, almost all groups submitted appealing websites and videos. Still, we observed clear differences in quality and creativity among the submissions. Some websites were very attractive, but a few groups included too many technical details, few pictures, and much text. Also, some videos did not present the product convincingly, but simply stated its features. We assume that these differences result from unfamiliarity with the submission formats. As intended, our website and video contest generated much interest. Although participation was voluntarily, 33 of 41 students voted for a website and a video.⁸

4 CONCLUSION

Covid-19 required us to reimagine a proven project design for an online environment. But after implementing our updated concept in 2020, it not only proved effective, but also increased the perceived quality of most student contributions, general engagement, and spatial and temporal flexibility. As a result, we continue using interactive online material, our final presentation formats, and Webots directly in summer 2021. To reduce overhead, we revert our milestone presentations back to a live format and adjust our feedback process. Students no longer have to ask questions after each presentation, but they receive bonus points if submit a small anonymous feedback form. Also, we require students to write only one detailed review. Despite its success, our updated project misses hands-on experience with physical hardware. Because this is key aspect of embedded systems development, we will reintroduce actual hardware once teaching in presence is possible again, but keep Webots for prototyping and testing.

⁸ All websites and the winning video can be found at https://www.sese.tu-berlin.de/menue/studium_und_lehre/studierendenprojekte/mpsees_ees_2020/parameter/en/

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